

University-Industry R&D Collaboration in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "University-Industry R&D Collaboration" in the context of the Global Innovation Index measures the level of cooperation between academic institutions and businesses in research and development (R&D). This indicator is crucial for evaluating a country's ability to transform academic knowledge into practical applications, innovative products, and technological solutions that drive economic growth and global competitiveness. Strong collaboration between universities and industries bridges the gap between theoretical research and practical application, fostering technology transfer and patent creation. Universities bring advanced scientific expertise and research facilities, while businesses provide financial resources, market experience, and commercialization capabilities. Together, these synergies promote the development of advanced technologies and innovative products. The level of collaboration varies significantly across countries, reflecting factors such as government support, the availability of R&D funding, and the culture of innovation. High R&D cooperation is often associated with a stronger innovation ecosystem, increased productivity, and enhanced international competitiveness. This indicator, therefore, serves as a key measure of a country's innovation potential and its ability to sustain knowledge-based economic growth. The data covers the period from 2013 to 2022.

University-Industry R&D Collaboration in 2022. The data on university-industry R&D collaboration from the 2022 Global Innovation Index reveals notable differences among countries, highlighting varying levels of integration between academic research and industrial innovation. The United States leads the rankings with a score of 79.6, demonstrating a robust ecosystem where universities and industries collaborate effectively to drive technological advancements and economic growth. This success is supported by strong public-private partnerships, well-funded research institutions, and a culture of innovation that facilitates knowledge transfer. Switzerland and Israel, both with a score of 77.6, are exemplary models of highly developed collaboration systems. Switzerland's score reflects its focus on applied research, while Israel's performance underscores the vibrancy of its startup ecosystem and strong ties between academia and industry in high-tech sectors. China, tied with the Netherlands at 70.1, shows significant progress, particularly in applied sciences and technology. Its substantial R&D investments and policies promoting partnerships between universities and businesses have strengthened its position in the global innovation landscape. Many European countries, such as Ireland (69.3) and Belgium (68.8), perform well due to strong government support and innovation-oriented industries. Similarly, Singapore, with the same score as Belgium, stands out for its advanced research infrastructure and policies incentivizing collaboration between academia and industry. Countries like Italy (58.2) and Vietnam (58.2) demonstrate moderate levels of collaboration, indicating room for improvement. In Italy, collaboration could be enhanced by greater integration between university research and market needs. Vietnam, on the other hand, is building an expanding innovation ecosystem but still faces structural challenges. Less developed economies, such as Angola (18.7) and Yemen (20.7), rank at the bottom, reflecting weak connections between universities and industry, often due to inadequate infrastructure, lack of research funding, and

political instability. Similarly, mid-sized economies like Iran (27.7) and Paraguay (26.8) show low scores, emphasizing the need for more effective strategies to promote technology transfer and better coordination between academic research and industry.

University-Industry R&D Collaboration from 2013 to 2022. The data on the variable "University-Industry R&D Collaboration" in the context of the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022 shows diverse dynamics across countries, reflecting different policies, economic structures, and investments in research and innovation. The best-performing countries include Algeria (+161.27%), Albania (+137.09%), and Guinea (+97.89%), which have made significant progress in both absolute and percentage terms. These improvements may be attributed to government initiatives aimed at promoting innovation, increasing research funding, and encouraging collaboration between academia and industry, particularly in developing economies striving to close the gap with more advanced countries. Countries such as Vietnam (+56.03%) and Azerbaijan (+47.65%) also show strong gains, indicating effective strategies in strengthening connections between academic institutions and productive sectors. These improvements likely result from policies focused on diversifying the economy and attracting foreign investment geared toward innovation. On the other hand, some traditionally strong innovation economies have shown stagnation or only slight improvement. For instance, Italy recorded a 32.57% increase—a positive outcome but lower than that of many emerging economies. Other developed countries, such as China (+24.73%) and the United States (+3.11%), experienced less pronounced increases, possibly due to a saturated market for academic-industrial collaboration or an already high starting level. On the negative side, many countries recorded significant declines. Among the worst performers are Bosnia and Herzegovina (-39.75%), Nigeria (-37.32%), and Nicaragua (-37.25%). These results highlight a reduction in interaction between academia and industry, likely caused by political instability, lack of research funding, or structural weaknesses in productive sectors. Even relatively developed economies, such as the United Kingdom (-22.47%) and Brazil (-21.86%), have seen significant declines, indicating that even established economies can face setbacks in strengthening these collaborations. Some advanced economies, such as Germany (-8.33%) and Japan (-11.92%), have shown reductions in academic-industrial collaboration. This trend might reflect shifts in economic priorities or decreased emphasis on traditional partnerships in favor of innovation driven by private companies.

Conclusions. The average value of the analyzed variable decreased by -1.04%, dropping from 46.63 to 46.15 units. The top-performing countries are Algeria (+161.27%), Albania (+137.09%), Guinea (+97.89%), Georgia (+80.95%), and Côte d'Ivoire (+68.86%). The worst-performing countries include Iran (-29.87%), Panama (-30.95%), Nicaragua (-37.25%), Nigeria (-37.32%), and Bosnia and Herzegovina (-39.75%).

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Best Performance	Algeria	14,2	37,1	22,9	161,27
	Albania	21,3	50,5	29,2	137,09
	Guinea	23,7	46,9	23,2	97,89

	Georgia	25,2	45,6	20,4	80,95
	Cote d'Ivoire	22,8	38,5	15,7	68,86
Worse Performance	Iran, Islamic Rep.	39,5	27,7	-11,8	-29,87
	Panama	51,7	35,7	-16	-30,95
	Nicaragua	35,7	22,4	-13,3	-37,25
	Nigeria	41,8	26,2	-15,6	-37,32
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	48,3	29,1	-19,2	-39,75

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